

Language Education for Asylum Seekers and Refugees in Italy: Provision and Governance

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2019

Executive Summary

1. In Italy, the acquisition of the Italian language is considered a fundamental step to guarantee access to the territory for a period of more than one year and the beginning of the integration process;
2. The teaching of the Italian language is entrusted to two channels: from the government side, it is provided by the Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA); these courses are supported by additional hours within the SPRAR system and in some CAS centres, for refugees who are part of an integrated reception project;
3. The Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA) are a type of autonomous teaching institution, with a specific didactic and organizational structure, divided into territorial service networks, usually on a provincial basis. They provide training for adults and young adults, of any gender or nationality, who have not completed compulsory education or have not obtained a final qualification of any level;
4. The Italian language courses within the SPRAR system are autonomously managed, responding to the needs of the migrants, by increasing the number of hours provided and ensuring continuity of learning during the summer period;
5. With regard to CAS centres, where possible, specific local projects are envisaged but not on a national basis, as with the SPRAR system;
6. The SPRAR and CAS network may implement protocols of intent with a CPIA for the enforcement of the education rights of refugees. These organizations contribute to refugees' enrolment in the school system, and the accompaniment of migrants in obtaining a diploma or university registration;
7. The governance of the system is sufficiently integrated between the State, local and third sector levels. The GLIMER team, however, noted the need for more resources (economic, but especially human capital) to strengthen language learning;
8. The training of teaching staff takes place at a national level but the educational approaches are deepened through practice and experience;
9. In recent years, the adoption of methods of self-certification of qualifications by migrants and the simplification of the processes of electronic recognition of diplomas has made it easier to continue the study programmes;
10. There is an ageing recruitment mechanism for teaching staff in the CPIA, which does not consider the large numbers of students and the high level of school drop-out during the learning period, but there is a requirement to include additional teacher support staff (e.g. mediators) to facilitate learning pathways.

1. Legal and Methodological Framework	1
1.1 The right to education of adult refugees at national and regional level	1
1.2 Language and higher education	2
1.3 Governance of the education system at local level	3
1.4 The right to education of children, unaccompanied minors and young refugees	4
1.5 Italy's approach to intercultural education: facts and figures	5
2. Language Training in the National and Local System	8
2.1 Provincial Centres of Adult Education	9
2.2 Language learning between the CAS and SPRAR system	10
3. Education and Integration in the National and Local System	11
3.1 Language education and citizenship	11
3.2 Language education and labour market integration	13
4. Education and Integration in the Local Case Studies	14
4.1 Provincial centres for adult education	15
4.2 SPRAR project	15
4.3 Extraordinary reception centres	16
4.4 Third-sector and local associations	17
5. Educational Practices in a Comparative Perspective	18
5.1 Local implementation of the right to education for unaccompanied minors	18
5.2 Teacher self-training systems for adults	19
5.3 "Informal" learning approaches as a social integration tool	20
5.4 Extracurricular education sites	22
6. Emerging Themes	23
Appendix A: National background and SPRAR System	25
References	26

1. Legal and Methodological Framework

Article 34 of the Italian Constitution states that "schools are open to all", recognising in a general and explicit way the right to study as a fundamental freedom of the human person and assuming, therefore, that it must be guaranteed by law to all legal subjects in a condition of equal treatment. The principles of this right are preserved in Articles 2, 3 and 4 of the Constitution. For this reason, education must be guaranteed and protected for all foreigners present in the territory of the State, both in terms of training, access to services and participation in the life of the school community, in accordance with the provisions of Article 38 of the Consolidated Act on Immigration (TUI).

In fact, what is established by Article 34 of the Constitution is to be assumed, as the Italian Constitutional Court has repeatedly confirmed, in the sense of its more complete centrality of the person, who becomes the "crossroads of that relationship between freedom, equality, human dignity and solidarity" (A. Sandulli, 2006). This approach goes beyond the more typical model, coming from the French Revolution, for which education was presumed as a public function and, therefore, considered as a mere instrument to achieve a governmental goal, than the way to achieve social equality.

The empirical research for this report was carried out by semi-structured qualitative interviews and by participating observation periods. The interviews (24 in total) involved social workers (1); educators (4) working for The Protection System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees so called SPRAR¹) projects dedicated to families and unaccompanied minors as well as social workers (2) responsible of Extraordinary Reception Centres for young people and families, located in the municipality of Cosenza and in the provinces of Cosenza and Catanzaro. Other interviews were addressed to cultural mediators/experts of migrant associations (4) in the city of Catanzaro; teachers of literacy (2) working in SPRAR and CAS² [*Centro di Accoglienza Straordinario*] centres in the province of Cosenza; members of humanitarian organizations and officers of the national reception system for refugees (2); teachers of the Provincial Centre for Adult Education of the city of Cosenza and the province of Catanzaro (5); assistants (2) and educators (1) engaged in the third sector to teach the Italian language to women refugees in the municipality of Cosenza.

Periods of participant observation were carried out at the CPIA in Cosenza attending classes in Italian pre-A1, A1 and A2 (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages). Several informal interviews were conducted with the teaching staff of the CPIA in Catanzaro. The interviewees were contacted both on the basis of their experience in the field of adult education and for the quality of the projects they have undertaken to implement innovative measures to safeguard the educational rights of refugees, including public-private cooperation.

1.1 The right to education of adult refugees at national and regional level

The situation of adults authorised to have access to the national territory is particular, even though they are guaranteed the right to learn the Italian language and are encouraged to continue their studies for anyone interested in doing so. At the same time, the knowledge of Italian is essential, especially because it allows the migrant to obtain

¹ It is a system of protection for migrants without subsistence facilities. The network is composed by local authorities which, through the National Fund for Asylum Policies and Services, implement integrated reception projects.

² These are temporary structures and limited to the time strictly necessary for the transfer of the migrants to the first or second reception centres.

a residence permit. In particular, a long-term residence permit is subject to the possession of a document certifying the applicant's linguistic competence. Already in the so-called "security package", approved by Law No. 94 of 15 July 2009, a real "integration agreement" was introduced in Italy (Article 4-bis of Legislative Decree No. 286/1998). Subsequently, the regulation governing this agreement (Presidential Decree no. 179/2011) came into force, and makes this new document fully applicable. After this legislative change, the integration model adopted by national policy has progressively moved towards a highly bureaucratic model, closely linked to the legislative regulation of residence permits. With the integration agreement, in fact, the migrant who applies for a residence permit (of at least one year) stipulates an agreement with the State authority (the Prefecture, in this case) that provides for the acquisition of a basic knowledge of the Italian language (level A2) and essential knowledge of constitutional principles and the functioning of state institutions. The agreement has a duration of two years and is based on a system of attribution of credits: the migrants must accumulate thirty credits in total, sixteen of which are attributed at the time of subscription. The applicant also undertakes to ensure that any children are following compulsory school.

To satisfy these requirements, starting from the 2014/2015 academic year, the Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA) were activated. The CPIAs are autonomous educational institutions and carry out the functions previously implemented by the Permanent Territorial Centres (CTP) and by the educational institutions that host evening learning courses. As will be seen below, these entities play a crucial role in the integration process and are currently the main body at local level that ensures the learning of the Italian language, including for employment. The regions play an essential role, working at the forefront of the implementation of initiatives that promote the integration and social inclusion of adult migrants. These initiatives, however, are strongly linked to the availability of the regional budget, "to the size of migration flows and the political feeling of administrators, which determine profound inequalities on the national territory in the enjoyment of a fundamental right such as that to education" (Biondi Dal Monte et al, 2017).

1.2 Language and higher education

Under the general legislation on the right/duty to education, a person is required to have an education for ten years and to be trained up to eighteen years, with the acquisition of a secondary school certificate or a professional qualification for a period of at least three years (Article 1, paragraphs 2 and 3, of Legislative Decree no. 76/2005). This specific obligation implies that at the age of majority, the foreign child, even if without documents, must not abandon his studies but may continue until he obtains the higher education qualification. Also, according to this law, when the migrant is 18 years old, he/she can still complete his studies: refusing this possibility would produce unreasonable results, considering that secondary school can be completed even after the age of majority.

In order to ensure a positive development of the learning process for all members of the school community, considering that there are no courses entirely dedicated to migrants, the distribution of foreign students in the classes limited to 30% of the total number of members enrolled in that class. This limit, provided for in a circular of the Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR), can be ignored only in 3 cases: 1) when foreign students are already fluent in the Italian language (for example, for foreigners born in Italy or who have started their educational career in Italian schools); 2) when they are foreigners without an adequate knowledge of Italian who need specific assistance for reasons of educational continuity; 3) in the case of classes already formed in the past year.

Article 39 of the Consolidated Act on Immigration (TUI) regulates access to university education for legally residing foreigners, which must be guaranteed under conditions of equal treatment with Italian citizens. In particular, TUI provides a "binary system" between foreign students already residing in Italy and students still residing abroad. Under this system, foreigners can access the university courses and specialization schools with a:

- EU long-term residence permit;
- residence permit for employment or self-employment,
- for family reasons,
- residence permit for political asylum, refugee or humanitarian reasons and for religious reasons;
- higher education qualification obtained in Italy and regularly residing in Italy for at least one year at the date of submission of the application form;
- final diplomas issued by Italian State and Equivalent Schools abroad or by international schools operating in Italy or abroad;
- valid residence permit for study purposes.

The procedure currently requires that after identifying the relevant course of study, the immigrant student sends a pre-registration request to the chosen Italian University within the deadline, delivering it to the Italian diplomatic-consular representation in his country or to the administrative office of the University, in the case of refugees. The application must be accompanied by a series of documents, officially translated into Italian. If they are not exonerated because they already have the appropriate certification, foreign students must also take an Italian language test, which is held at the university chosen following the calendar published on the website of the Ministry of Education. Those who have not passed the Italian language test cannot be admitted to the additional tests. Foreign students attending University are granted a residence permit for study reasons, now for one year, renewable if they continue to be enrolled at the university, if they have taken a certain number of exams and if they continue to satisfy the requirements relating to financial support, until the conclusion of their studies and, in any case, not after three years beyond the duration of the degree course.

Several local initiatives in Italy have been identified in the higher education sector. The Association of European Universities (EUA) has listed 15 Italian universities developing actions to improve refugee access to higher education in Bari, Naples, Rome, Teramo, Siena, Bologna, Turin, Pavia, Verona and Trieste (Gaebel & Zhang, 2018). In May 2016, Italy was the first European country to adopt the so-called "#U4Refugees" initiative (now, University for Refugees), in order to create special "educational corridors" for students and researchers. Finally, the Ministry of the Interior, in collaboration with CRUI (Conference of Rectors of Italian Universities) and ANDISU (National Association of Organizations Promoting the Right to Education at the University Level), has offered 100 scholarships to students benefiting from international protection, to facilitate access to higher education programs, starting from the academic year 2016-17.

1.3 Governance of the education system at local level

In Italy, specific functions are assigned to provinces only for higher secondary education (15-19 years) Municipalities, which often represent small residential communities and areas with restricted access, operate across the country and have responsibilities or delegated powers at the local or provincial level for functions and services relating to

child education, primary and middle schools. Provinces and municipalities carry out their specific educational functions through dedicated educational offices (Councillorships) [Assessorati].

As regards the admission of foreigners and refugees at local level, the role played by individual educational institutions is very important. The Ministry of Education (MIUR) establishes a general framework for school autonomy in order to ensure the uniformity of the Italian education system. In fact, the Ministry of Education sets: the general objectives of the educational process; the specific learning objectives for the competences of the pupils; the subjects of the national minimum curriculum; the annual number of teaching hours; the quality standards of the educational services; the general criteria for the evaluation of the pupils; the general criteria for the organization of the study paths of adult education. Each school, therefore, offers something different.

The Training Provision Plan (POF) is the basic document that defines the cultural and project identity of the school. It must be coherent with the general and educational objectives of the various courses of study and specialisations set at national level. At the same time, it must reflect the cultural, social and economic needs of the local level. The POF is drawn up by the College of Teachers on the basis of the general objectives defined by the Provincial School Council and considering the proposals and opinions of the organisations and associations of parents and, only for the higher secondary level, of the student associations. The POF must be approved by the Schools Provincial Council and given to the students and their parents at the time of enrolment. In this document, for example, it's possible to find the directions that each school wants to follow and the educational approaches that will be used towards foreign students. As consultants, the Associations managing the integrated reception projects (SPRAR) and the cultural mediators can be consulted.

In addition to the Headmaster and the Administrative Manager, the role played by the Provincial Council and the School council are very important for the choices relating to the educational integration of foreigners is the role played by two bodies: the Provincial Council and the School Council. The Provincial Council and the School Council (in comprehensive schools³ and secondary schools [11-19 years]) are composed of elected members of teaching and non-didactic staff, parents and, at the secondary level, by students. The Headmaster is an official member. The president is elected among the parents' representatives.

The two Councils decide on the organisation of school activities, while respecting the functions of the Teachers' Council. They provide a general framework for the elaboration of the school's training plan (POF) and approve it. The College of Teachers is composed of permanent and temporary teachers of each Province or institute. It is chaired by the director of the school. It formulates the POF according to the general management and administration guidelines issued by the Provincial and School Council.

1.4 The right to education of children, unaccompanied minors and young refugees

Article 38 of the Consolidated Act on Immigration (TUI) applies all current provisions on the right to education, access to educational services and participation in the life of the school community for foreign minors, but also guarantees access to learning courses, in primary and secondary schools, to adults migrants with a regular residence permit, as well as the ability order to obtain the diploma of compulsory schooling (MIUR-INDIRE, 2014).

³ A Comprehensive Institute brings together in the same organization a nursery school, a primary school and a secondary school close to each other in terms of geographical location.

Foreign students under the age of 18, who enjoy the same rights as natives, are included in the classes corresponding to their age, except where the teachers' board decides differently. Also for them, the 30% rule applies to the total number of pupils enrolled, with possible derogations that the Headmaster may choose to apply. Moreover, all schools are required to equip themselves with all the resources needed (e.g. mediators, updating courses for teachers) to promote rapid learning of the Italian language. To address these needs, in 2014 the MIUR approved the new "Guidelines for the reception and integration of foreign students" (MIUR note of 19/02/2014) providing, especially for newly arrived students, intensive modules of eight or ten hours per week with a duration of three or four months. If the student does not have any personal documents, he or she can still be enrolled at school because the right to education cannot be restricted by the condition of irregularity. Reporting the presence of the undocumented student by school operators is not required. Consequently, the school may or may not do this. Foreign minors are still considered the same as Italian minors in terms of the right to education, even if in there are specific paths for language acquisition.

Concerning unaccompanied minors, access to the education system and training is of fundamental importance for the regularisation process, whether or not they are seeking asylum. In the second case, upon reaching the age of 18, the unaccompanied minor has the right to remain in Italy only if he/she is a beneficiary of international protection. However, the repeal of humanitarian protection under Legislative Decree 113/18 (the so-called Salvini Decree) seriously jeopardises the regularisation of unaccompanied minors, who mostly benefitted from this level of protection.

Research into support processes for unaccompanied minors suggests that most minors attend Provincial Adult Education Centres (known in Italy as CPIAs) (Giovannetti 2012; Bichi 2008; Campani et al. 2002). However, there are no statistics regarding their presence in the adult education system. Statistics on adult education from a 2012 monitoring report show that young foreigners aged 16-17 attending courses for adults make up 7.2% of the total number of foreign students enrolled, with those aged 18-19 making up 8.3%. In particular, the highest proportion of students is enrolled in first-cycle education courses (primary school courses and lower secondary diploma courses), with 19.5% of these students aged 16-19; 13-15% of these young people are enrolled in courses for linguistic and social integration, in short modular functional literacy courses, and in second-cycle courses (Pappalardo & Rangoni, 2013).

1.5 Italy's approach to intercultural education: facts and figures

At the national level, the approach to intercultural education has been introduced in ministerial notes and other decrees of the CNPI (National Council for Education), an advisory body of the Ministry of Education. The process was designed to address an emergency situation that required rapid and pragmatic responses. Volunteering and lack of political orientation have characterized the transition of the Italian education system towards a multicultural approach (Peticari, 2008; Serpieri & Grimaldi, 2013; Crocetta, 2016).

As recently observed (Bussotti, 2017), the period of affirmation of multicultural education in Italy can be divided into four phases:

- Naive phase of universalism
- Phase of mixed principles (universalism + relativism + individualism)

- Phase of rediscovery of Italian diversity
- Complexity phase

These four phases are not necessarily in chronological order. In fact, each of them prevailed for a short period of time, although the other principles were also present.

The Italian educational system, therefore, has focused on the substantial adaptation of content and objectives, considering the initial attitudes, skills, talents or areas of intervention of each student (Baldacci, 2006). Moreover, a quick analysis of the documents published by the Italian institutions, which first reveal the complexity of the school system, clearly shows the distance that separates the new frontiers of education from what is done in practice. It is clear that intercultural education is understood exclusively as "emergency approaches for foreign students" (Catarci, 2010).

In fact, the introduction of the intercultural didactic approach as a pedagogical tool is found in the Ministerial note of 8 September 1989, n. 301, which is fundamental for the academic inclusion of the children of migrants. The circular emphasizes some points of fragility of the Italian system, until then unprepared to deal with cultural diversity, as well as for educational activities not oriented to differences. The necessary involvement of social and associative training of immigrants in the planning of operational practices is therefore beginning to be discussed. All this is inspired by the vision of a school that acts synergistically with the bodies that deal with the protection and assurance of other social and health services (Law no. 943/86). For this reason, "memoranda of understanding" and inter-institutional operational projects that use and enhance every force present in the territory have been created. The intercultural pedagogical approach of teaching was then taken up by Ministerial Circular no. 73 of 2 March 1994, which shifted the focus on intercultural dialogue and democratic coexistence, giving a specific role of mediation between different cultures not only those of which the pupils are carriers.

In a 2007 report, the Ministry of Education summarized the principles on which multicultural education has been based in recent years: universalism, "common education", intercultural approach, centrality of the person in relation to others and exaltation of relativism. All these concepts have been proudly recalled in this document as the key aspects of the Italian way to intercultural education (MIUR, 2007). Four years later, as mentioned above, in a context of growing concern, the MIUR documents continued to follow the same line of action as in 2010. The line of action was and still is: to avoid high concentrations of foreign students, to involve families and to teach "Citizenship and Constitution" as a basic subject for a better integration of foreign students. At the same time, the MIUR has detected a new phenomenon: a growing presence of foreign students in high schools. There has also been a high number of abandonments, which has caused serious concern.

According to the latest Report on foreign students in Italy (MIUR, 2018) more than 40% of fourteen-year-old students with non-Italian citizenship are behind in terms of education. As far as young people aged 18-24 are concerned, most of them are at high risk of dropping out of education. The delay of foreign students can also be attributed to slowdowns due to non-admission and repetition: in fact, the results of the survey on the integration of second generations (ISTAT, 2016) concerning foreign secondary students of the High school degree are significant, from which it emerges that the delay involves 76.9% of the subjects and, of these, almost 30% was inserted at least two years behind the class corresponding to their age. The MIUR also makes an interesting comparison between Italian students and students of migratory origin, however, highlighting that in the A.S.

2016/2017 at national level, Italian students who are late in school attendance at secondary school represent 20.9% compared to 59.1% of students with non-Italian citizenship (MIUR, 2018).

An alarming consequence of late education is undoubtedly the abandonment of school attendance. This phenomenon has been analysed through the European indicator of *Early Leaving from Education and Training* (ELET)⁴, which shows that foreign students are those at higher risk of dropping out, with a number equal to 32.8% compared to a national average of 13.8%, in turn 1.2 percentage points away from the European target 2020 equal to 10% (MIUR, 2018).

In any case, following the reform of the school system that was launched in 2015, at least one of the teachers have the task of improving the knowledge of the Italian language by immigrant students. For the first time, in fact, in the public competition of 2016 for the selection of permanent teachers, teachers specialized in teaching Italian to foreign students were hired for the first time.

In Calabria, according to the data of the latest Ministerial Report (MIUR, 2018), of a total school population of 282,663 enrolments, the presence of foreign students amounts to 12,458 units. This figure, however, should be added to the presence of foreigners in the Calabrian CPIAs, which is highly difficult to detect. In the Province of Cosenza, for example, the Ministry of Education finds a total of 4,067 foreign students of which: 635 in pre-school, 1,274 in primary school, 879 in middle school and 1,279 in high school.

For the same reference period (2016/17), the CPIA of Cosenza recorded an estimated and potential number of users of 31,790 immigrants (CPIA Cosenza, 2017), which obviously does not include users of the SPRAR system, that during the same period hosted about 1,140 people (CITTALIA et al, 2018). This is certainly interesting and can be evaluated in relation to secondary education: in Calabria, out of a total of 4,011 foreign students, 1,055 chose high schools (liceo), 1,648 technical schools and 1,308 vocational training. The paths chosen by these students show, more clearly, the channelling towards the technical and professional schools that occurs since the transition from one level of secondary education to the next (MIUR, 2018).

⁴ The *Early Leaving from Education and Training* (ELET) indicator refers to the proportion of 18 to 24-year old with qualifications of secondary education who are not in vocational training programmes.

Figure 1: Italian Educational System - Source: Eurydice 2019

2. Language Training in the National and Local System

The instruments that guarantee the knowledge of the Italian language and the continuous and constant learning of professional skills come from the obligation that every migrant has to sign the so-called "integration agreement" (Article 4-bis of TUI) in order to obtain any authorization to stay in Italy for more than one year. It is, in fact, a "compulsory integration process" introduced by law (Law No. 94/2009), which induces migrants who wishes to live and integrate in Italy to satisfy some obligations to prevent, in the most serious cases, the sanction of expulsion.

The agreement works with a credit allocation system, of which 16 are assigned at the time of subscription. This document is signed at the Immigration Desk [*Sportello Unico per l'immigrazione*] of the Prefecture or at the police headquarters, according to the reasons for the admission. The agreement is signed at the same time as the application for a residence permit and has a single fundamental purpose: to achieve over a two-year period a level of integration corresponding to no less than 30 credits, assigned on the basis of the active participation of migrants in assured training activities. If this level is not reached, the agreement may be extended for a further year.

Therefore, the knowledge of the Italian language and culture represents the central element of the integration agreement: by signing the agreement, the migrant starts to acquire a knowledge of the Italian language spoken equivalent at least to level A2 of the common European framework of reference for languages issued by the Council

of Europe. For its part, the State accepts to support the process of integration of foreigners through the assumption of any appropriate initiative in collaboration with the Regions and local authorities.

It should also be noted that this agreement is verified at its expiry with a specific proof and the presentation of documentation that certifies - unequivocally and legally recognized – the educational achievements of the migrant and his integration into the national territory. For this reason, since 2009, different channels of language and professional learning have been identified that allow foreigners to facilitate their integration, as well as to comply with legal obligations. Migrants with disabilities that severely restrict self-sufficiency, unaccompanied foreign minors and victims of trafficking and/or torture are exempted from the agreement

2.1 Provincial Centres for Adult Education

The Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA) are a type of autonomous school institution, with a specific didactic and organizational structure, divided into territorial networks, usually on a provincial basis, in accordance with regional school planning. All foreigners, from the age of sixteen, can access specific training courses. These school structures offer all the services and activities of education and training for all adults in the local area and start from cultural and linguistic literacy to professional reskilling.

Each CPIA has a group of teachers and a network manager, who analyse, plan and implement initiatives and courses of lifelong learning for young people and adults. The activities of the Centres, are not usually concentrated in a single location but are developed throughout the province, in structures that are chosen in agreement with the local municipalities.

The CPIA is open to adults, including foreigners, who have not completed their compulsory education; those who have already completed the first cycle of education and who intend to complete the second cycle of education; foreign adults who wish to join the paths of literacy and Italian language learning; young people, including foreigners, who are over the age of 16 and who, having completed their first cycle of education, cannot attend the courses during daytime.

Literacy and Italian courses for foreign adults are designed to obtain a qualification attesting to the level of knowledge required for Italian no lower than level A2. The second-level education courses, however, are finalized to the attainment of a diploma of technical, professional and artistic education and are implemented by the State educational institutions of the province. After this course it is possible to obtain a qualification in the Italian language: the courses of the CPIA at A2 level (or higher) are the only ones recognized by the Ministry of the Interior for long term residence permits.

Starting from 2015, six Provincial Centres for Adult Education have been activated in Calabria: Catanzaro, Cosenza, Crotone, Vibo Valentia and two for the province of Reggio Calabria; each Centre branches out into different peripheral locations that guarantee the coverage of the service on the whole territory, with a total presence of about 30 adult schools at regional level (MIUR, 2018).

Knowledge of language is crucial for socio-economic integration because it makes people independent and able to satisfy their needs independently. Enrolled foreigners have to take an entrance test before the literacy courses.

According to the latest Report on immigration in Italy, 108,494 of foreigners were residing in Calabria on 31 December 2017 representing 5.5% of the total population, compared to a rate that five years earlier was set at 4.4% (IDOS, 2018). This data, although largely respected by the estimations, cannot be exhaustive in describing the reality on the ground. Foreigners arriving in Calabria come from different migration channels (e.g. sea landings, forced migration, integrated and extraordinary reception network, internal movements). For this reason, a complete mapping of the population attending these centres cannot be obtained. The CPIAs, in fact, are a choice not only to speed up the integration process, but an obligation to obtain any residence permit.

To try to understand the characteristics of the users who frequent these centres, we can focus on some figures: at present, the province with the highest number of immigrants is Cosenza, with 35,559 people, Reggio Calabria follows with 32,870; with regard to gender, women in Calabria represent 49% of residents. However, we must always consider the specific type of residence permit, which also gives details of the migrant's possible location on the territory: 49,300 migrants in Calabria hold residence permits, of which 52% have a long-term permit and, among the temporary permits, 45.3% have obtained permits for refugees and humanitarian reasons (IDOS, 2018).

It is important to specify that each Provincial Centre in the region provides literacy courses, first and second level courses, but within the limits of its Three-Year Training Plan (TOPF) which are the documents used to indicate in advance the implementation and the estimated costs of language inclusion projects. In addition to the pyramidal organization over which the Regional School Office (USR) supervises, the CPIAs of Cosenza, Crotona and Vibo Valentia have decided to create a network through the integrated management platform called CPIAGEST. This network for the management and sharing of practices was set up as part of the MIUR Project for the experimental application of products developed as a result of activities and interventions carried out by the CIA (Ministerial Decree 663/2016). The platform allows one to manage the data of the students, as well as the registration procedure in the various locations, to organize courses and calendars, generate real-time statistics, monitor attendance and simplify and standardize the process of certification.

The six CIA of the region, in collaboration with the Region of Calabria and in partnership with the USR, promote the project "Calabria Friends", aimed at the implementation of Italian language courses and civic education for foreigners from outside the EU regularly present in the territory, including unaccompanied foreign minors. The project, financed by the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund 2014-2020 (AMIF), has as its specific objective integration and legal migration, as part of the more general national objective of integration of the immigrant population. Regarding staff training, we have observed a progressive specialization compared to the first years of implementation of the centres through the adoption of more specific texts for immigrants and the incorporation of more specialized personnel that are more sensitive to these topics. However, it should be underlined that the allocation of teaching staff in these Centres is based on the enrolment/diploma ratio: this calculation can generate some critical problems, especially if we consider that many foreigners begin to attend the language course but do not complete the training until obtaining their certification.

2.2 Language learning between the CAS and SPRAR system

The teaching of the Italian language and communication skills can also be improved by the foreign national within the reception centres in they have been placed. Currently, the main initiatives for the education and literacy of migrants are carried out by the SPRAR and CAS systems, alternately and continuously with the hours scheduled by

the CPIA. In many of the cases analysed, migrants are followed in two different steps: a part of the day is dedicated to school attendance within the CPIA and the remaining hours will be spent on personalized training in the host centres.

With regard to the SPRAR system, language learning and training are two of the objectives contained within the so-called "hosting pact" [*Patto d'accoglienza*] that the beneficiary signs individually with the association that manages the SPRAR centre. This mechanism therefore includes this action among the objectives to be achieved within a personalized integration project that the SPRAR operators implement directly for the migrants. During 2017, at the national level of the 22,452 beneficiaries who have continuously attended at least one Italian language course, 19.5% followed a pre-literacy course (A1), 38.3% a basic course (A2), 24.4% an intermediate course (B1) and 11.2% an advanced course (B2). In the same reference period, the beneficiaries who instead completed the courses and obtained a certificate of attendance recognized at regional and national level (e.g. CPIA), were an average of 13.8 per project. In most cases, a basic course (39.3%) was completed, along with an intermediate course (29.6%), pre-literacy (11.6%) and, finally, an advanced course (11.4%). In the SPRAR system, at least one linguistic-cultural mediator is systematically present in the centres. This is a professional who works across the various services and supports the work of the entire team, facilitating internal and external communication processes and accompanying the beneficiaries along their integration paths. Significantly, mediators are 76.2% of the Project staff. (CITTALIA et al, 2018).

In the projects analysed, the beneficiaries take part every week in at least 10 hours of Italian language lessons in total between the course held by the SPRAR teacher, the CPIA lessons of Italian for foreigners and the parallel help provided by the operators within the hosting project.

The CAS system also consults with the CPIAs and educational institutions. As in the case of SPRAR, there is no internal integration pact within the Centre but, in the cases analysed, language learning activities through the accompaniment of the migrant in situations that can stimulate the use of a specific language (e.g. accompaniment in offices, simulation of real situations) are nevertheless profitable. In these cases, the migrant must make the credits provided for in the so-called integration agreement, only for those who are over 16 years of age.

3. Education and Integration in the National and Local System

3.1 Language education and citizenship

Since 2005, language education in the Italian school system has been strongly linked to an accurate and certified knowledge of the current institutional, political and administrative system in Italy (Boccagni & Pollini, 2012). For this reason, the civic education programme of the Italian A2 level course indicated by MIUR and the Ministry of the Interior includes: Italian history and constitution, central and territorial institutions, citizens' rights and duties, training, health, housing and other practical information oriented towards the stable integration of a new citizen. These guidelines are carried out, with autonomy of resources and programs, by the different schools of first and second level, as well as by the Centres for Adult Education (CPIA).

While the Ministry of Education has been focusing heavily on increasing civic education at all school levels in recent times, this teaching is not always considered to be equal to the humanistic disciplines (Eurydice, 2019). In every

school program there is the possibility to include a module called "Citizenship and Constitution", carried out over two hours per month entrusted to the professor of history but, in concrete terms, not much attention has been dedicated to the actual development of these topics, because it is not required for any final evaluation.

In any case, as regards migrants who wish to apply for a residence permit of more than one year and for refugees who access the reception system (and sign the so-called "integration contract") it is necessary - as for the certified knowledge of the Italian language - to know about civil and political rights, the functioning of the Central State and the Constitution. This test, which is carried out in order to obtain the certificate to be linked to the application for a residence permit, is also proposed for foreigners who want to obtain a permit for long term residents.

However, since December 2018, the Ministry of the Interior and the Ministry of Education (MIUR) have been implementing some changes in this field that will inevitably affect immigration policy. As regards the teaching of so-called 'civic education', a draft law is currently being discussed by the Culture Committee of the Chamber of Deputies, drafted in four articles which provide for the following measures: 1) a total of 33 hours per year, to be entrusted to teachers in the historical-geographical area in secondary schools and to teachers in the economic-legal area in secondary schools; 2) an annual prize for civic education to reward the best experiences in civic education at all levels of education. Civic education will be the subject of an interview during both the middle grade exam (14 years) and the oral exam to complete higher school (18 years).

On the other side, with regard to the acquisition of Italian Citizenship, Law no. 132/2018 introduced a number of changes that concern the specific field of competence in language skills: starting from December 2018, in fact, the acquisition of Italian citizenship by marriage (art. 5) and by legal concession or naturalization (art. 9) is subordinate to the foreigner's possession of an adequate knowledge of the Italian language, not lower than level B1 of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Until this reform came into force, a wider, even if certified, attestation of integration within the Italian State was required, which was discretionarily evaluated by the Public Administration. With the recent amendments, in order to demonstrate this knowledge, at the time of filing the request, applicants are required to certify the possession of a degree delivered by an institution of state or equivalent education, recognized by the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (e.g. CPIA). Alternatively, applicants must submit an appropriate certificate of knowledge of the Italian language, provided by a recognised institution accredited by the Ministry of Education (MIUR) and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MAECI). Currently, the only institutions authorized to grant this certificate are: University of Roma Tre, the University for Foreigners of Perugia, the University for Foreigners of Siena and the Italian Cultural Society "Dante Alighieri".

People who have signed the integration agreement and holders of long-term residence permits are excluded, since these are situations for which the law already requires an assessment of their knowledge of the Italian language at the end of the integration process. The increase in the level of certification from A1 to B1 only for the acquisition of Citizenship creates an unjustified disparity in treatment between immigrants, only on the basis of the qualification required (Di Maio, 2018).⁵

⁵ However, it should be noted that since many years the Ministry of the Interior, the Ministry of Education and the company Rai Education have created a website to teach Italian civic culture to migrants. The website is funded by the European Fund for the Integration of Foreigners from outside Europe (Caneva, 2014, 13).

3.2 Language education and labour market integration

In Italy, the improvement of language skills in order to facilitate admission into the labour market considered - at governance level and from the legislative point of view - as a complementary element to language training. For this reason, like the learning of the Italian language, professional training is provided both through the Centres that are responsible not only for adult education, but also through the reception projects involving associations of the third sector.

The CPIA can, first of all, extend the range of training offered within the framework of their autonomy, in accordance with the competences envisaged for the regions and local authorities, also making use of agreements that the municipalities or regions can stipulate with other public and private entities (e.g. training structures accredited by the regions).

The improvement of the training on offer consists of additional activities, which must be coherent with the aims of the CPIA and meet the needs of the cultural, social and economic context of the local areas (e.g. initiatives to integrate and enrich the adult education pathways, encourage the connection with other types of education and training programs). For example, the agreements may include partnerships with lifelong learning pathways, vocational education and training programmes (leFP), traineeships, higher technical education and training (IFTTS) and technical specialization pathways (ITS). These three types of school structures are organised in a network, which is linked to the "National Network of Services for Labour Policies" (art. 1.2 of Legislative Decree no. 150/2015).

In order to facilitate the attainment of a qualification or a professional diploma by migrant adults, the CPIAs can make connections between the first level paths and the apprenticeship paths, in compliance with the criteria and guidelines established by the provincial or regional coordination, maintaining the competence of the Regions in the matter to provide specific scholarships or integration programs for long-stay migrants, foreigners with residence permits for work reasons and refugees.

In the SPRAR projects, however, professional training is provided through personalized paths and finalized to the acquisition or updating of theoretical and practical skills (e.g. carrying out specific professional roles, recognition of previous skills). The SPRAR manual of each project includes courses for the first-time introduction, qualification, retraining, specialisation, updating and further training of foreign workers.

However, each individual project enjoys complete autonomy in carrying out these activities. For this reason, the financing of vocational training programmes is usually supported by European, regional or territorial grants (SPRAR, 2018). In the professional education field, it is possible to distinguish between: courses co-funded by the European Social Fund (ESF); courses activated by the national system of lifelong learning; residential courses (with accommodation and subsistence included) and courses finalized to the fulfilment of the training obligation (SPRAR, 2016). Until now, the Italian legal system has recognised the possibility for applicants for international protection to attend professional training courses which, if necessary, can also be carried out by the local authority which is responsible for the reception project. However, it should be noted that there are serious problems caused by the recent entry into force of Law n.132/2018, which excludes access to SPRAR reception projects for all immigrants who are waiting for a form of international protection (e.g. asylum seekers).

Each SPRAR territorial project, in any case, can begin and consolidate a continuous relationship with the training institutions operating in the area to verify the training on offer through an adequate mapping and provide agreements that follow the access of beneficiaries to the courses. Such formal or informal agreements, where the training offer does not sufficiently address the needs of the SPRAR beneficiaries, may start with a proactive role of the local authority responsible for the hosting project or several associated local authorities.

Figure 2: Short overview of the Italian reception system before the Law n. 132/2018

Source: www.asylumineurope.org

4. Education and Integration in the Local Case Studies

In Calabria, immigrants residing on 1 January 2018 represent 5.5% of the population, with 108,494 people who have chosen the regional territory as their usual residence (ISTAT, 2018). However, it should be highlighted that for the purposes of this research, this figure can only be descriptive but not exhaustive. Refugees, asylum seekers and other types of migration covered by this study do not very often represent (or do not constitute) the resident part of the population because most of them move to other territories or other Member States of the European Union.

In any case, it is useful to know that the largest immigrant community is from Romania with 32.5% of all foreigners present on the territory, followed by Morocco (13.6%) and Bulgaria (6.2%); with regard to, however, the nationality of migrants who are used victims of forced migration, in the Calabrian region we can highlight that few of them remain permanently as residents: 2.24% comes from Nigeria, 1.45% from Senegal, 1.34% from Mali and only just

Figure 3: Calabria - Most important municipalities © Glimer Project

over 0.9% from Afghanistan and Iraq. Other interesting data concern stateless persons (0.02%) who are however very few due to very favourable legislation on residence permits and acquisition of citizenship (ISTAT, 2018).

4.1 Provincial centres for adult education

There are currently 32 provincial centres for adult education in Calabria, currently, are 32 (MIUR, 2018) grouped by province. Our research focused on the two provinces of Cosenza and Catanzaro, which have a density of migrants present on the territory of 5.02% and 5.3% respectively, a figure that is increasing by more than 4% compared to previous years (ISTAT, 2018).

The **CPIA of Cosenza** was founded in 2015 following the reform of the CPT and consists of an administrative office in Cosenza and is divided into 11 associated offices in different schools across the province, 4 penitentiary offices that will form the network RIA (Network Education for Adults) together with the vocational schools (22) which have a relationship of cooperation. Currently, about 900 students can be enrolled in Italian language literacy courses for foreigners with a staff of 48 teachers (CPIA Cosenza, 2018).

The **CPIA of Catanzaro** was also established in 2015 and has an administrative office in Catanzaro, supported by 7 associated offices located in the province, 6 penitentiary offices that make up the RIA network along with 11 schools in the vast territory. Starting from the school year 2017/2018, this institution has promoted the creation of the Regional Centre for Research, Testing and Development, in consortium with the regional CPIAs. This consortium discusses and implements specific teaching and reception guidelines aimed specifically at the foreign population. Currently, it is possible to identify the presence of 188 foreign students, with a greater predominance of students from Morocco (29%) and Nigeria (21%) [CPIA Catanzaro, 2018].

4.2 SPRAR projects

SPRAR is one of the inclusion tools provided for by Italian law, to which a foreigner enjoying international protection can have access in the case of inadequate living conditions. With Law no. 189/2002, the Ministry of the Interior established the system's coordination structure - the Central Service - and entrusted its management to the National Association of Italian Municipalities (ANCI). The SPRAR is composed of a network of local authorities that, through the National Fund for Asylum Policies and Services (FNPSA), carry out integrated reception projects. The system is not limited to a purely welfare reception but is aimed at integrating people in the territory through reception in small towns developing personalized projects. Currently, after the adoption of Law no. 132/2018, the system is suffering from numerous changes, starting with the beneficiaries who can access these services. In the current reform process, only refugees and foreign minors can be accommodated in the centres. Applicants for international protection are excluded.

Since 2005, **La Kasbah** has been the Managing Body of the SPRAR project “Asylon, Cosenza: the welcoming city”, owned by the Municipality of Cosenza until 2009 and owned by the Province of Cosenza, from 2009 to today. The association provides services for asylum seekers and those receiving humanitarian protection, single men and families (not belonging to vulnerable categories). The experience started from the recovery of a former road-keeper’s house owned by the Province, located in a rural area in the Cosenza hinterland, used for the spontaneous welcome of the Kurdish families who arrived in Calabria in the 1990s. The legal and administrative office of the Asylon project is in a disused school building, on whose premises it is possible to glimpse the work of local artists and refugees who embellish a physical place characterised by a collective social

use where everyone has the right to move around. The “G. Comisso” Legal Office is present here, active weekly and free for migrants and refugees in the area; in the afternoon, on the other hand, the educators of the project are dedicated to after-school activities for the children of refugees.

Since 2012, the Cooperativa Il Delfino has been managing social inclusion and assistance projects for migrants. As part of the SPRAR programme, today it is the association that provides services for the SPRAR Centre for Foreign Minors in Mendicino, a premontane town in the province of Cosenza, which is now held up as an example of integration and cooperation for refugees. The authority responsible for the project is the Municipality of **Mendicino**, which also offers facilities for educational and integration activities. In this context, there are several activities that involve the indigenous population along with foreigners. Since 2015, the same association also manages a project specifically aimed at foreign adults in the municipality of **Pedace** (Cosenza). In this specific project, in addition to the basic services provided by the SPRAR guide, the association is dedicated to the identification and recovery of people in a serious situation of vulnerability (e.g. victims of trafficking and torture).

In the pre-mountainous area of the Cosenza hinterland, the SPRAR Project "Migrasud", was launched in 2016 and is managed by the association "Strade di Casa" and for which the Municipality of **Rovito** is responsible. This project was created to join the integrated reception and has developed over time many projects focused on the literacy of migrants, with particular attention to their integration into the labour market.

The SPRAR project "La Casa di Abou Diabo" has been active in the northern area of Cosenza since 2008. The Municipality of **Acri** is responsible for the project, in collaboration with the association Liber Accoglienza. Given the structure of the territory and the presence of schools, the association is particularly dedicated to the linguistic and occupational integration of immigrants, also promoting direct meetings with students and foreigners to encourage participation.

The SPRAR project "Luna Rossa" of Lamezia Terme, in the province of Catanzaro, was born in 2011 and has been part of the integrated reception since 2014. This initiative was created in a place where the presence of foreign minors is strongly incisive. In fact, its services are almost exclusively oriented towards the educational and linguistic inclusion of immigrants and young refugees. In addition to personal support, the association has established a wide network of relationships with entrepreneurs and other associations in its territory to promote professional education and the acquisition of new working skills.

4.3 Extraordinary reception centres

According to the Law no. 142/2015, if the availability of places inside the structures of first and/or second reception is full, it is possible for the Prefect to take extraordinary measures of reception, in temporary structures and limited to the time that is strictly necessary for the transfer of the asylum seeker to the structures of first or second reception. With regard to the management of extraordinary reception centres (CAS), different and partly contradictory indications have been given on how they should be structured, due to numerous notes and rules of engagement. Firstly, there was a tendency to merge the services offered in the CAS to SPRAR services in order to favour the progressive passage within the ordinary protection system (e.g. Note of the Ministry of the Interior dated 11/10/2016 and Note dated 04/08/2017); secondly, with the new specifications (starting from the decree of the Ministry of the Interior dated 7 March 2017), there was an incentive for a model based on large collective

structures, which is parallel to, but not necessarily integrated with, the SPRAR network. Today, most of the displaced migrants received in Italy are concentrated in CAS (Openpolis, 2018).

Since 2014, in the heart of the historical centre of **Cosenza**, there is the extraordinary reception centre "San Martino", a structure that was initially created to welcome minors who have been abandoned and that is now part of the extraordinary reception circuit. The association responsible for managing it has set up a special protocol with the first level secondary school "Tommaso Campanella" in Cosenza, which provides guests with afternoon language and literacy courses, while two days a week a literacy course is guaranteed in the centre. During the free time, artisan workshops and agricultural activities are organized in the small garden in front of the school.

Since 2016, in the pre-mountainous territory of the Cosenza district, there are two other extraordinary reception centres called CAS "Hobbit" and CAS "Due Torri" which have been established in agreement with the Prefecture of Cosenza and the Municipality of **Dipignano**. In these structures, there are also measures of personal assistance for the migrants and language literacy courses, integrated with the courses held by the nearby CPIA. The association Il Delfino, which manages other reception projects, tries to standardize and make more accessible the services, given the involvement in the two reception circuits, the extraordinary one (CAS) and the integrated one (SPRAR).

4.4 Third-sector and local associations

Since 2018, a multifunctional centre for the integration and social inclusion of legal immigrants has been operating in **Cosenza**. The centre, managed by the social community La Terra, is located in one of the oldest buildings in the historic centre of the city, made available and renovated by the Municipality. In the building there is an area of socialization and recreation, together with an adequately equipped space where language training workshops are carried out. The association to which the management has been entrusted organizes moments of inter-religious coexistence. In addition, legal advice, health and administrative guidance services are available. The centre is a place of observation on the phenomenon of immigration in the city and in the province, as well as a location for the planning of cultural initiatives. The service is mainly aimed at minors and families. The Centre was projected through a partnership between the Municipality of Cosenza and the Service Centre for Volunteering of the Province of Cosenza, a third sector organization, founded by the Management Committee of the special funds for volunteering of the Calabria region in 2003 and in implementation of the Framework Law on Volunteering (Law no. 266/91).

Founded in 2014 in the territory of the Province of **Catanzaro**, the social promotion association ASIM (Immigrants Association) promotes initiatives and projects to support the integration, inclusion and reception of people from foreign countries, stateless persons and asylum seekers. It is aimed in particular at young migrants and families. It carries out cultural mediation interventions in the areas of Education, Health, Work for the provinces of Catanzaro, Cosenza, Crotona, Reggio Calabria and Vibo Valentia. It has also activated an information desk and activities of legal advice and cultural linguistic mediation in the province of Catanzaro. The project *Il lavoro per l'inclusione* [Work for Inclusion], in partnership with the Municipality of **Soverato** and financed by the Region of Calabria, is of particular relevance in the context of initiatives designed to promote the integration of foreign citizens.

5. Educational Practices in a Comparative Perspective

5.1 Local implementation of the right to education for unaccompanied minors

In the Italian legal system, all children under the age of 14 can access the education system in relation to their academic achievements. An initial assessment of the unaccompanied minor's current level of education is carried out in the residential community through the preparation of the Individualised Education Plan (PEI). The choice of upper secondary school is based on an assessment of the young person's expectations and his/her academic record by the residential community's social worker.

In the education plan, you find out what school the asylum seeker attended in their country, and you often stick to what they tell you, because you can't accurately confirm it in any case. Then you choose together based on their wishes and aspirations...
(Social Worker, Int. n. 5)

The construction of the unaccompanied minor's identity as a young adult between the worlds of school and work opens up fundamental questions about a school system that, while apparently open to cultural diversity, seems in reality to contribute to issues of educational segregation among non-Italian children, particularly young people who have to support themselves and meet familial expectations. For unaccompanied minors who can access upper secondary education (usually those who have already completed lower secondary school to the age of 14), the main obstacle is that the protection process ends when they come of age. According to statistics from the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy, most of the minors in residential communities are 16-17 years old and therefore find

Figure 4 Teaching workshop @ Starde di

themselves unable to complete the "integration programme". Interviews with teachers and social care professionals reveal that dropping out of school is a widespread phenomenon among unaccompanied minors, as is running away to destinations in Northern Europe. Despite their period of schooling in Italy, these minors frequently end up becoming the most vulnerable immigrant workforce in the informal labour market.

If the minor does not have a lower secondary education certificate, the school committee can decide to admit the child following a written and oral exam aimed at demonstrating his/her knowledge (Article 192, Paragraph 3, Legislative Decree no. 297/1994). However, the accounts provided by educators and social workers indicate the difficulty of communicating with schools, with access often being strictly dependent on the minor being in possession of a lower secondary education certificate. Consequently, most unaccompanied minors aged 16-17 are not eligible to enrol in upper secondary school and usually attend an initial basic Italian course in CPIA (A1 and A2 Italian) as well as a course that prepares them to take the lower secondary school exam. Based on interviews, it appears that CPIAs are often their first experience of education, allowing them to escape the "ghettoising" cohabitation of their residential community. However, the location of CPIAs in neighbourhoods on the outskirts of city centres pushes unaccompanied minors into a different kind of "ghetto", since young Italian students are so few and far between there.

5.2 Teacher self-training systems for adults

Research in the field has focused on places where refugees and asylum seekers learn Italian: CPIAs in the provinces of Cosenza and Catanzaro; integrated reception projects run by SPRAR; and the temporary reception centres where Italian language courses are held in the province of Cosenza. CPIAs are responsible for issuing certificates to non-Italians stating the level achieved in Italian as an L2 (second language). Since 2015, following the exponential rise in the number of asylum seekers and refugees in the provinces of Calabria and the closure of the Permanent Regional Centres (CTPs), the student population of CPIAs in the provinces of Cosenza and Catanzaro has been largely made up of beneficiaries of international and humanitarian protection as well as legally-residing immigrants. The first group mostly includes young men (aged 16 and above), mainly of African origin (West and Central Africa), with some from India and Pakistan. The long-term residents include migrants from the Maghreb (especially men) and migrant women from Eastern European countries.

The interviews reveal that the ability of migrants to learn Italian differs across the board based on their prior schooling, which is linked in part to their geographical origin. There is a particular focus on the low level of education among refugees from Africa, on their first experience of schooling and their "different" language skills (they speak various languages... they don't know how to read and write, they learnt the language through immersion Int. n. 6), and on the difficulties of getting a qualification recognised for those who do have an upper secondary school diploma.

The Syrians we've had have usually had quite a high level of education, or at least a decent level, whereas the Africans haven't. Many of the Africans aren't literate; they haven't been educated. I work at the first reception centre now. It's a great experience because I have the group of illiterate students (there's a lot of us, it's shared between three colleagues). The students are from different countries: Guinea-Bissau, Senegal, Mali. They haven't been educated: they've been to Islamic school but don't know how to read or write in their mother tongue, so they didn't know the Latin alphabet. They speak various languages but can't write. They've learnt the language through immersion, by being in the countries, but they don't know the alphabet – they're not familiar with reading or writing. (Teacher Int. n. 6)

CPIA teachers come from a primary school teaching background or from specialised university courses. They are given refresher training as part of a regional programme specifically aimed at training teachers of Italian as a second language.

In the interviews, CPIA teachers distinguish between their "institutional" training and the applied teaching phase. Government training involves participation in workshops and seminars: regional and national meetings between CPIAs on teaching strategies and methods for the inclusion of foreign learners. The teaching experience in class reveals the difficulties inherent in forging individualised pathways in the absence of psychological/medical personnel; the impossibility of completing the reception process (the student interview) without a cultural mediator; and the high student turnover rate. Classes are overcrowded (particularly those leading to a lower secondary education certificate), while attendance is inconsistent. Absences are also caused by a failure to allocate transport resources, which severely limits the ability of beneficiaries of both SPRAR and temporary reception centres to attend CPIAs. The interviewees highlight the dynamics at play whereby migrants are excluded from access to resources. The picture painted is one of educational spaces strictly separated from the classes open to Italian students, located in urban suburbs with large immigrant populations or in outlying areas that are difficult to reach by public transport. The interviews with SPRAR social workers and CPIA teachers paint the ghettoization of adult education spaces as

a practical and social characteristic of the racism that teachers have been experiencing in their professional everyday lives.

Educators' reports of their experiences describe classes with students of various ethnicities where teachers must become skilled in decoding gestures and behaviours, mediate the difficulties of dialogue between ethnicities, and understand gender disparities (in some cases educators teach families, encouraging husbands to allow their wives to attend). Students sometimes use in the classroom the Calabrian dialect they have learned in their daily activities and the teachers start from this to introduce some concepts of the Italian language, using different examples.

Teachers must "step outside their domain" and the closed-off world of their own teaching and work collaboratively with CPIA colleagues, building networks across the region through agreements with various local refugee reception projects. In the latter case, with regard to the Cosenza CPIA, the agreements consolidate synergistic actions (both formal and informal) through which to teach others – and ourselves – to develop a critical mindset opposed to preconceived ideas and attitudes, as well as consolidating a shared sense of responsibility among all those involved in the field of education (Elia, 2017).

It takes time... It can happen that a young person gets to the end of their studies and we still haven't been able to understand anything about the individual. The most common attitude that I encounter is a closed-off, repressed mindset... All of them have very difficult life experiences in their past.

(Teacher Int. n. 7)

We're the school of networks... we have maybe 30-40 agreements... then we do the Calabria CPIA network for AMIF projects, we do agreements with municipalities that sometimes give us premises, if we don't have a deal with the school... we do agreements with SPRAR, with associations for migrants...

(Teacher Int. n. 7)

Unfortunately, numbers have gone up exponentially... sometimes, CPIA teachers call us to resolve problems related to administrative practices, healthcare identification and other procedures for students in their classes... Since 2011, this has become standard practice...

(Educator In. n. 8).

5.3 “Informal” learning approaches as a social integration tool

Figure 5 Informal activities for migrants
© Polifunzionale Cosenza

In the reception centres analysed, learning Italian becomes a daily exercise: from cooking (sometimes shared with the teachers) to visiting the doctor and using public transport. In the initial orientation phase, the beneficiary's profile is mapped out. Beneficiaries are tested on their level of education through interviews in which they provide information on where they are and how long they might have to wait for the hearing. This involves using the Italian language as a tool, and the migrants' first teachers are the social workers employed by the reception projects. These are women who interface with young men, unaccompanied minors who have just come of age, and families: teachers of Italian as a second language, but also educators and social workers. In many cases, teachers of Italian as a second language are not an integral part of the team managing services targeted at applicants for international protection.

These female teachers are considered a stable point of reference. From the statements collected, it becomes clear that their experiences of teaching young male migrants who attended Islamic schools vary; as women, female teachers are not discriminated against. The status attributed to these individuals, who operate in parallel with the public education system for adults, is that of an important point of reference: people to be relied on due to the very position they hold, i.e. educators.

For young adult refugees (between 20 and 25 years old), the time spent learning brings meaning to the "wait", a sort of initial gatekeeping method which educators tend to direct towards awareness-raising strategies (Sen, 1988). They encourage beneficiaries to pay renewed attention to themselves and their own expectations. Beneficiaries do not "voluntarily" go to the CPIA; attendance at Italian language classes must be included as a clause in the social inclusion programme and subsequently accounted for in the work integration plan.

They go to school (to the CPIA) because they get reprimanded otherwise, but then they go and they want to have backpacks and purses bought for them; just think, it's often the first time they've been to school. (Social Worker Int. n. 9)

Where children haven't been able to complete their schooling in their own countries, the Teaching Centres give them the chance to finish their studies with the lower secondary certificate. This qualification gives them more opportunities when looking for a training apprenticeship or a job placement... We've just finished a training apprenticeship at a tax assistance centre. In these cases, if you have a qualification, the employer not only accepts you for the apprenticeship, but might even be more inclined to draw up a work contract for you. (Social Worker Int. n. 10)

The interview reports highlight the need to offer students constant motivation to keep learning Italian. There are multiple reasons for this: overcoming the traumas of the journey; the lack of education in their home country, which acts as a powerful emotional barrier because they now find themselves in a society where this situation is a major handicap; and problems with the regularisation of their legal status. The interviews with educators/teachers describe the ways in which refugee women and men show their resistance to what is envisaged (according to Knudsen 1991) as a means of rehabilitating the beneficiary; a sort of "sweet", "gentle" violence – to use Bourdieu's categories (2003) – that is "symbolic" for the way in which it places the responsibility on the refugee to adhere to the paradigm of linguistic integration in a context in which the migrant does not want to remain (Elia 2018).

First of all, many of them are victims of torture and post-traumatic stress disorder, so it's already difficult to follow a personalised pathway... many are older, so going back to studying is really difficult... And it's not like when you move to a foreign country and decide to sign up for a language course. They're forced to flee, so you're obliged to learn the language of the new country; you have no choice. (Educator Int. n. 11)

The people in the Centres run by the System for the Protection of Asylum Seekers and Refugees, and above all those in the Temporary Reception Centres, are adults who have significant experiences in their past, they have problems with documents, the commission decides not to issue the document, not to give them any protection, so they're always telling you: Miss, too many problems, too many worries... (Teacher Int. n. 4)

5.4 Extracurricular education sites

The experiences of linguistic inclusion analysed focus in particular on the educational inequalities facing refugee women, recreating what Ambrosini (2004) defines as "educational sites rooted in the local area". They develop tangible responses from the ground up, self-activating in the face of a lack of resources or staking out a space for negotiation with local institutions. The Immigrants in Italy Association (ASIM) has its headquarters in Catanzaro city centre. The ASIM team is made up of cultural mediators (both male and female) with front-line experience of working towards educational integration for adult migrants and children of migrants since the '90s.

Currently, ASIM does not receive any form of funding from local institutions. It has been involved in designing literacy courses aimed at migrant women and refugees in the city centre since the Catanzaro CPIA was transferred to the outskirts of the city. The aim is to offer a presence in the local area and also to act as a help desk, often replacing local institutions.

During the 1990s, migrant associations were allocated specific funds as key players in the implementation of social integration initiatives, including access to social/educational services (Caponio and Dota 2000). Over the years, migrant associations, even those coordinated across multiple countries, have not received legal and political recognition, despite Law no. 39 of 1990 acknowledging the value of collective action by migrants.

The women in particular are desperate... their husbands are also unemployed... it was different before... even the employee who had different political ideas didn't reveal them, now everything changes like the wind... (Cultural mediator, ASIM)

The interviews with educators working for SPRAR in the provinces of Catanzaro and Cosenza suggest that refugee women there live in conditions of isolation. The "language barrier" prevents them from opening up independently to their new situation, and they are forced to rely on their husband or children. The teachers and social workers also attest to the infrequent CPIA attendance of pre-A1 students, who are almost totally absent from classes preparing learners for the lower secondary exam. They often attend classes with their young children, accompanied by their husbands, sometimes as students themselves.

We talked about it with some teachers from the CPIA, and they told us that there are actually no Moroccan or Syrian women attending the CPIA. There aren't many women full stop; the only ones are Polish and Romanian. The few women and mothers who do attend have their husbands waiting outside – the wife goes to school and the husband stays outside for the entire lesson. So, we realised that it's actually a situation that needs to be analysed very carefully. (Social Worker, Int. n. 7)

At the Multi-Purpose Centre in Cosenza, attendees learn Italian in a female community: female educators and social workers, refugee mothers and Italian mothers. Refugee women learn Italian by reproducing their domestic environment: the cooking workshop; motherhood; taking care of their children, who attend the Centre's nursery. This approach breaks down a system designed to protect humanitarian rights that "privileges male-dominated 'public' activities over the activities of women, which take place largely in the 'private' sphere" (Fenster 1999, 6).

The educators and social workers interviewed maintain that these women need to reinvent themselves and deconstruct the binary depiction of the poor and vulnerable refugee woman vs. the modern and emancipated western woman (Kelly 2000). In this female world, learning the Italian language starts with gaining an awareness of

the multiple forms of discrimination that affect refugee women and deny them equal opportunities from an educational standpoint: “Gender intersects in complex ways with issues of class, race, language, trauma and educational backgrounds” (Hatoss & Huijser, 2010).

The thing we've found with the Italian course is that the mums want to be alone with other women... we noticed it when talking to their husbands... we've had to reinvent ourselves too, and this is the beauty of what we do at the multi-purpose centre. We listen to the mums who come here and try to understand their needs, so it's almost like we structure the activities based on who they are... The cooking workshop works and creates this kind of relationship... they prefer to come to lessons here instead of going to the CPIA... staying near the nursery where their children are... (Social Worker n.1, Polifunzionale, Cosenza)

The practices implemented underscore an ongoing search for methods through which literacy teaching for migrant women can be incorporated into a broader process of "raising awareness" that aims to support the integration of female refugees locally, freeing them from the fear of communicating, the fear of having to reveal their past experiences, and the “shame” of not being able to learn to read and write.

Alongside the Pro Locos (local associations founded to promote and develop the local area), we decided to organise a cooking course where refugee women could cook and explain dishes from their home countries in Italian... lots of women took part... (Teacher L2, Strade di casa)

There was a moment when we were cooking Moroccan desserts and this Moroccan woman wrote down the ingredients in proper Italian. An Italian woman from the local neighbourhood said, "You can write!"... We said: "Yes, of course, she knows how to write in Italian". It was a Moroccan cake. When this local woman read the ingredients, she said: "Ah, those are the same ingredients I use to make ciambella!". (Social Worker n.2, Polifunzionale, Cosenza).

6. Emerging Themes

- The learning of the Italian language is perceived as a fundamental element both in the policies and in the different levels of governance.
- The migrant who requires international protection, however, needs to be motivated to learn and to follow an educational path. Difficulties in obtaining a residence permit and the extreme bureaucratisation of the procedure mean that learning Italian is often low down in the list of priorities for displaced migrants.
- Teaching staff are sufficiently trained, especially if younger, but have to deal with a very high work-load as a result of a lack of resources and high number of beneficiaries, both in the public and private sectors. Nevertheless, the Language Teacher is perceived as a point of reference by the immigrant in the integration process.
- The interviews show an association between geographical origin and educational level. For example, women from Eastern European countries seem to have a higher cultural and educational background than those from some Central and Sub-Saharan African regions. This phenomenon prompts social workers and teachers to consider the experience of trauma and their legal precariousness as a strong obstacle to the acquisition of Italian language.

- Field analysis shows high illiteracy rates among young and adults coming from Sub-Saharan Africa but also from some areas of Pakistan and Afghanistan. Some are almost totally illiterate and often unable to write characters of the alphabet. These are people who, despite speaking more than one language, are not able to write. It is necessary to proceed to the so-called reset courses or Pre-A1 and often the reception time is too short to allow students to reach level A1 or A2 and obtain a certificate of secondary school education.
- Generally, from the interviews it is possible to see how the learning of the Italian language is strongly linked to migration projects and to the perspective of a real labour market integration. The period of reception in Italy, especially for adults, is experienced as a step of the migration project whose final destination are countries such as Germany, France or the countries of Northern Europe.
- Calabria is not perceived as a territory that offers real opportunities for stable and regular employment, with very low attractiveness indexes in the area.
- One of the most burning questions, regarding the use of Italian language learning both to support the application to receive international protection, and for the purpose of a possible social and labor integration, concerns the novelties introduced by Law no. 132/2018. The new tenders for reception centres for applicants for international protection have, in fact, completely removed the obligation to teach the Italian language and the possibility of starting training courses.

Appendix A: National background and SPRAR System

ANCI: National association of Italian municipalities	[Associazione nazionale dei comuni italiani]
ANDISU: National Ass. of Organizations for Education' Right in the Universities	[Associazione Nazionale delle organizzazioni che promuovono il diritto all'istruzione a livello universitario]
CAS: Extraordinary reception centres	[Centro di accoglienza straordinaria]
CEFR: Common European Framework of Reference for Languages	[Quadro Comune Europeo di Riferimento per le Lingue]
CNPI: National Council for Public Education	[Consiglio Nazionale della Pubblica Istruzione]
CPIA: Provincial Centres for Adult Education	[Centri Provinciali per l'Istruzione degli Adulti]
CRUI: Conference of Italian University Rectors	[Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università Italiane]
CTP: Permanent Territorial Centres	[Centri Territoriali Permanenti]
EUA: European Universities Association	[Associazione delle Università europee]
FAMI: Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund	[Fondo Asilo, Migrazioni e Integrazione]
FNPSA: National Fund for Asylum Policies and Services	[Fondo nazionale per le politiche e i servizi di asilo]
FSE: European Social Fund	[Fondo sociale europeo]
IeFP: Vocational Education and Training Institutes	[Istituti di Istruzione e Formazione professionale]
IFTS: Institutes of Higher Technical Education and Training	[Istituti di Istruzione e Formazione Tecnica Superiore]
ITS: Institutes of Technical Specialization	[Istituti di Specializzazione Tecnica]
MAECI: Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation	[Ministero degli Affari Esteri e della Cooperazione Internazionale]
MIUR: Ministry of Education, University and Research	[Ministero dell'Istruzione, l'Università e della Ricerca]
POF: Training offer plan	[Piano dell'Offerta Formativa]
PTOF: Three-year Plans for the Training offer	[Piani Triennali per l'Offerta Formativa]
RIA: Adult Education Network	[Rete d'Istruzione per Adulti]
SPRAR: Protection System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees	[Sistema di Protezione Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati]
USR: Regional School Office	[Ufficio Scolastico Regionale]

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This project has received funding in the framework of the Joint Programming Initiative Urban Europe, with support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant No 693443.

